

***SGT1* Gene Expression Levels of Solasonine in Two Nigerian Eggplants (*Solanum melongena* and *Solanum gilo*) and Implications on Edibility**

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Submission: 21st January, 2024; Accepted 30th January, 2024; Published: 28th February, 2024

Abstract

One of the most popular vegetables consumed worldwide is the eggplant. However, it contains a secondary metabolite, glycoalkaloids (GAs), which can potentially impact human health, especially if their concentrations exceed the standard for food safety. This study determined the production ratio of solasonine (a glycoalkaloids) content and its expression patterns by solasodine galactosyltransferase (*SGT1*) gene in ten samples of matured eggplant (*Solanum melongena* and *Solanum gilo*) in Nigeria by employing Zymo-RNA extraction kit. Generally, analysis revealed a statistically significant differences among different cultivar types of eggplant fruits ($p < 0.0001$). However, there is a significant decrease of *SGT1* transcriptional expression in fruits of different cultivar types with increase in maturity levels. The highest mass percentage of solasonine production (3.87) was detected significantly in sample B having a lower Quantification cycle (Cq) of 36.41, while the lowest was in NC (0.65) with Cq of 38.81. Meanwhile, some samples showed no solasonine production indicating no *SGT1* expression. These observations imply that some of the samples used in this study, especially those with high solasonine production, are not suitable for human consumption.

Keywords: Bitterness, Eggplant, Glycoalkaloids, *SGT1* gene, Solasonine

1.0 Introduction

Being a member of the Solanaceae family, *Solanum melongena*, also referred to as eggplant or aubergine, is a vegetable crop with significant commercial importance that grows in both tropical and temperate climates. It is the most popular vegetable worldwide, along with potatoes and tomatoes [1]. Garden eggs are one of the most widely grown crops in Nigeria, and they have a ready market in both urban and rural areas [1]. In order to supplement the essential nutrients in the human diet, garden egg fruits and leaves are eaten as vegetables. The garden egg fruit is a good source of dietary fibre, potassium, calcium, phosphorus, and vitamins A and C. According to Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) [2], the fruits of a garden egg can be used as a garnish or eaten raw, as well as cooked, grilled, fried, or boiled. Additionally, in some parts of Africa, the leaves and blossoms of specific garden egg

species are used to flavour soups and stews. According to Santos et al [3], garden eggs have the potential to enhance nutrition, boost food security, foster rural development, generate income, and also support sustainable land use in Africa. Eggplant is a low-fat, low-cost food source that provides protein, energy, fibre, and vitamins, but it is also being investigated as a source of health-promoting metabolites, such as antioxidant and nutraceutical chemicals [3].

Glycoalkaloids and saponins, which give eggplant its distinctively bitter flavour and are usually recognized as anti-nutritional chemicals that may be harmful to humans because they prevent nutrient absorption, are present in eggplant [4]. A major role in the plant's defence against pests is played by a class of secondary metabolites called glycoalkaloids (GAs), which are frequently found in the Solanaceae family [5]. GAs have a wide spectrum of pharmacological activities, which

include anticancer potential, despite being hazardous to humans at certain dosages [6, 7]. Many GAs have acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitory action, which has been linked to the treatment of disorders like Alzheimer's disease (AD), Myasthenia gravis, and glaucoma, and also insecticidal and anthelmintic pharmacological processes [8].

It's well known that alkaloid accumulation and storage differ depending on the kind of alkaloid. Plants manufacture alkaloids in various tissues which is where the biosynthetic genes required for a specific alkaloid are expressed [9]. Alkaloids may be collected at the site of synthesis or be transferred to a particular tissue such as leaves damaged by insects or herbivores after production [10, 11]. Solasonine is a glycoalkaloids found in *Solanum* plants of the family Solanaceae. When used in excessive doses, solasonine is a chemical molecule that is poisonous [12]. Glycoalkaloids like solasonine have a number of uses in pharmacology, cancer treatment, and even pest control. As a result of their capacity to impair cell-membrane function, glycoalkaloids are hazardous to humans in high concentrations [12]. There is a loss of membrane integrity because each material that comes into contact with the cell has the potential to cause apoptosis (cell death) [13].

The main glycoalkaloids found in potatoes, solanine and chaconine (along with the solanidine aglycone), are extremely toxic and have been linked to some severe intoxications in people [14]. They can bind to membrane sterols, damage cell membranes, inhibit acetylcholinesterase, and disturb acid-base equilibrium *in vivo*. However, this level needs to be re-evaluated for glycoalkaloids other than solanine because the activity of each compound can differ from the others and because synergistic effects between different glycoalkaloids can occur [14]. Informally established guidelines limit the total glycoalkaloids concentration in potatoes to 200 mg/kg of fresh weight. The triglycosides R-solamargine and R-solasonine are the main glycoalkaloids of the common eggplant fruits [15]. They have the same aglycone (solasodine), bound to the trisaccharide chacotriose [R-L-rhamnose 1f4 (R-L-rhamnose 1f2) β -D-glucose] for R-solamargine, and solatriose [β -D-glucose 1f3 (R-L-rhamnose 1f2) β -D-galactose] for R-solasonine [16]. SGAs are generally produced on all parts of the eggplant, as well as the leaves,

roots, fruits, and sprouts, and biosynthesis occurs through the leaves, roots, fruits, and sprouts [17].

The *SGT1* (Solasodine Galactosyltransferase) gene identified in two species of peanut are located on chromosomes 5 and 9, encoded proteins ranging from 303 to 371 amino acids [18]. The gene which is known to be involved in the synthesis of solasonine from solasodine and also solasonine glycoalkaloids' (SGA) accumulation in eggplant, has not been the subject of many studies and the impact on human of consuming these eggplant cultivars. Since eggplants (*S. melongena* and *S. gilo*) consumed in Nigeria are grown to maturity, this study focuses on the expression levels of solasonine contents in ten samples of two species of matured eggplants and how their consumptions could affect the well-being of human. This will give pertinent information to help make better use of these species as food crops.

2.0 Materials and methods

2.1 Plant Materials

A total of 10 matured fruit samples of *Solanum* gotten from Ketu Market, Lagos, were collected and used in this study. The collections consist of 6 samples of *S. melongena* and 4 of *S. gilo*. Fruits samples of *S. melongena* occur in purple, green and white colours while those of *S. gilo* occur majorly in green and a mixture of both green and white. All samples were identified at Lagos University Herbarium (LUH), voucher number (SM13022024) collected. Samples were properly washed with distilled water to remove impurities that might be present and residual moisture dried with a paper towel. The samples were then labelled accordingly.

2.2 RNA Extraction

Zymo-RNA extraction kit manufactured by Zymo Research Company was used by following the procedure as outlined by the manufacturer. Firstly, each fruit sample was ground to form a homogenate. The homogenised sample was transferred into a ZR Bashing Bead Lysis Tube and 800ul of RNA Lysis Buffer added to it. The tube was processed for 20mins using a Disruptor Genie and then the tube with the homogenised sample was centrifuged at 10,000g for 1 minute to separate debris from supernatant. The supernatant was thereafter transferred to a Zymo-Spin™

IICG in a collection tube and centrifuged. The flow-through was then saved. The flow-through was then mixed with 95% ethanol in a 1:1 ratio and mixed well. After that the mixture was transferred into a Zymo-Spin™ IICR Column in a collection tube and centrifuged. The flow-through was discarded. The column was thereafter washed with 400µl of RNA Wash Buffer and centrifuged. The flow-through was once again discarded. Thereafter, 80ul of DNase I-DNA Digestion Buffer mix was added directly to the column matrix. This was allowed to incubate at 20-30°C for 15mins. 400µl of RNA Prep Buffer was added to the column and centrifuged. The flow-through was discarded. 700µl of RNA Wash Buffer was added to the column and the column was centrifuged. The flow-through was discarded and 400µl of RNA Wash Buffer added to the column. The column was centrifuged afterwards for 1 minute to ensure complete removal of the wash buffer. Thereafter, the column was carefully transferred into a nuclease-free tube and 50ul of DNase/RNase-Free Water added in directly and centrifuged. A Zymo-Spin™ II-HCR Filter was placed in a new collection tube and centrifuged afterwards. The filtered RNA is now suitable for qPCR and other downstream applications.

2.3 Spectrophotometry

Ribonucleic acid (RNA) quality and quantity were determined using Nano-drop spectrophotometer

(model 6305 JENWAY). This was carried out at absorption ratios: A260/230 and A260/280.

2.4 Complimentary DNA Synthesis

Complimentary DNA synthesis was done using FIRE Script Reverse Transcriptase(RT) cDNA synthesis Kit. Components were briefly mixed and spun down. Preparation of the cDNA synthesis reaction: 1µl of RNA, 0.5 of OligoT, 0.25 of dDNTPmix, 2 10x Rxn buffer, 0.5 of RT. 0.25 of nuclease free water to make up 10µl. Incubation of the reaction was carried out as follows: Reverse Transcriptase 60°C for 30mins, Enzyme inactivation 85°C for 5mins.

2.5 Real Time Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction (qPCR)

Using the Bio-automation Mermade 192E, the polymerase chain reaction primer sequences were generated based on the SGT1 gene, which corresponds to the gene. Cyclophilin (*CYP*) was used as a reference gene and sample NC was chosen as the control. PCR primers were synthesised at Inqaba Biotech Nigeria (Table 1). Real time quantitative polymerase chain reaction was performed using RTqPCR Thermocycler. The reactions were done in duplicates/sample/primer pair using the Luna® Universal One-Step RT-qPCR Kit (NEB, Catalogue No. E3005) following the conditions presented in Table 2 below

Table 1: Primer Description, Sequences and Temperature

Gene	Gene description	Primer sequence (5'–3')	tm/°C	Amplicon length/bp
SGT1	Solasodine galactosyltransferase	F:ATACCAGCCAAGAATGTTGTT R: CATTTCGAGGTGTTATCTT	58	134
CYP	Cyclophilin	F:ATCCTGTCCATGGCTAATGC R: ATGCCCTCAACAACCTGTCC	58	119

Table 2: PCR Reaction Volume

COMPONENT	Volumes for a 10µL reaction
Template RNA	1 µL
10µM Forward Primer	0.4µL
10µM Reverse Primer	0.4µL
Luna Universal One-Step Reaction Mix (2X)	5U1
Luna WarmStart® RT Enzyme Mix	0.5ul
Nuclease free water	2.7 µL

The tests were carried out in two technical duplicates, and the program CFX Manager v.3.1 was used for the gene expression assay. With a final volume of 10 µL for each reaction, the quantitative real-time PCR (qRT-PCR) amplification was performed using a real-time PCR system (Biorad CFX-96). This system included 1 µL of the previously diluted cDNAs, 5 µL of Luna Universal One-Step Reaction Mix (2X), 0.5 µL of Luna WarmStart® RT Enzyme Mix, 10 µM of each forward and reverse primer. The qRT-PCR temperature program was set at 10

min at 55 °C and final melting curve between 60 and 95 °C.

The tubes were thereafter spun down to collect the liquid and placed in a real-time instrument programmed as shown in Table 3. The products

were analyzed by melting-curve analysis by 60°C - 95 °C with an increment of 0.5°C every 0.05 seconds. This quantification program was followed by a melting point for every PCR product and for each sample.

Table 3: The PCR Profile

Step	Stage of PCR	Temperature (°C)	Time (min: secs)
	Reverse Transcription	55	10:00
1.	Initial Denaturation	95	1:00
2.	Denaturation	95	0:10
3.	Extension	60	0:30 (+ plate read)
4.	Melt curve	60-95	Various

2.6 Gene Expression Fold Change Calculation

The target gene *SGTI* Cq was normalized with the *CYP* Cq. The mean of Cq values of *SGTI* gene and mean of Ct values of *CYP* were then compared. The calculation was based on $\Delta\Delta Ct$ or Livak method [19]. The formulas of Livak method was calculated using excel sheet and fold change values of all the eggplant samples were calculated as compared to reference gene and also as compared to control eggplant (Pointy and Flat) sample.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

Graphpad 9.3.1 (Graphpad Software Inc. California, USA) was used for all data analysis.

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test were used to determine the significance between groups. The statistical significance was defined when $p < 0.05$.

3.0 Result

Samples collected and their morphological parameters are shown in Table 4 below.

Collections include four samples of *S. gilo* and six of *S. melongena*, with colour ranging from green-white, green to purple. They also come in different shapes from round, wide-pointy to wide-oblong and oval.

Table 4: Collected Eggplantsamples and their morphological characteristics

Samples	Plant	Colour	Phenotype
A	Garden egg (<i>gilo</i>)	Green and white	Round
B	Garden egg (<i>melongena</i>)	Green	Wide and pointy
NC (Control)	Garden egg (<i>melongena</i>)	Green	Pointy and flat
D	Garden egg (<i>melongena</i>)	Purple	Wide and oblong
E	Garden egg (<i>melongena</i>)	Green	Round and pointy
F	Garden egg (<i>gilo</i>)	Green and white	Round and fat
G	Garden egg (<i>gilo</i>)	Green and white	Oblong and pointy
H	Garden egg (<i>melongena</i>)	White	Wide and flat
I	Garden egg (<i>melongena</i>)	Green and white	Oval
J	Garden egg (<i>gilo</i>)	Green	Oblong and oval

The result of the purity analysis of the isolated RNA from group A, B, NC, D, E, F, G, H, I and J are shown in (Table 5). The lowest purity of 101.2 was shown by sample G and the highest of 1562.8

by sample NC. Figures 1 and 2 show the absorption peak of RNA samples extracted from eggplant fruits (*S. melongena* and *S. gilo*) at wavelength of 260/280 and 260/230.

Table 5: Spectrophotometric Reading of the RNA extracted from different fruit samples.

Sample Types	Concentration	A260/A280	A260/A230
A	813.6	2.04	2.12
B	1525.8	2.05	2.08
NC (Control)	1562.4	2.01	2.06
D	545.3	2.02	1.86
E	1810	2.07	2.16
F	588	2.08	2.06
G	101.2	2.09	2.06
H	285.1	2.09	1.89
I	582.2	2.11	2.17
J	157.2	2.08	1.95

Figure 2: Absorption Peak of RNA Samples of F, G, H, I and J at Wavelength of 260/280 and 260/230.

The result of gene expression presented using clustergram is shown in Figure 3, which revealed the hierarchical levels at which the gene was expressed. The expression of *SGT1* gene was only visible in samples B, NC, E and J but more in sample B (red). Also, the result of gene expression as shown in table 6 revealed that group B showed the highest expression of *SGT1* gene

with value of 3.87 while the lowest expression was in sample NC with value of 0.65.

SGT1 expression profiling was carried out in eggplant cultivar types. Generally, analysis revealed a statistically significant differences among different cultivar types of eggplant fruits ($p < 0.0001$). However, there is a significant decrease of *SGT1* transcriptional expression in

different cultivar types of eggplant fruits in respect to control group as shown in clustergram.

Figure 3: Clustergram of *SGT1* Gene Expression in Different Cultivars of Egg Plant Fruit.

Figure 4 show the fold change (FC) in expression of *SGT1* gene normalized to *CYP1* gene. Sample B showed significant decrease in *SGT1* transcriptional expression in respect to control group ($p < 0.0001$) and a fold change decrease in expression of (FC= 0.17). Sample E also showed a significant decrease in expression in respect to control group of (FC= 0.71; $p < 0.0001$). Similarly, a decrease in expression is seen in Sample J of (FC= 0.65; $p = 0.0045$). Furthermore, other samples also showed a decrease in expression of *SGT1* gene in different cultivar of eggplant fruits with a fold change decrease in expression of zero (FC= 0) compare to control group.

Figure 4: The Fold Change Difference in *SGT1* Gene Expression of different Cultivar of Egg Plant Fruits Normalized to *CYP1*.

* indicate significance difference between sample types

**** $p < 0.0001$

*** $p < 0.0005$

** $p < 0.005$

Table 6: Expression level of *SGT1* Normalized to *CYP* Gene in Different Cultivar of Eggplants Fruits

Sample	Solasonine production as a result of <i>SGT1</i> Expression (%)	Quantification cycle (Cq)	SEM
A	N/A	N/A	N/A
B	3.87	36.41	0.00
NC	0.65	38.81	0.00
D	N/A	N/A	N/A
E	0.91	36.55	0.00
F	N/A	N/A	N/A
G	N/A	N/A	N/A
H	N/A	N/A	N/A
I	N/A	N/A	N/A
J	0.99	40.02	0.00

NA = Not Applicable

Values are means of two (2) replicates and standard error of mean (SEM).

4.0 Discussion

The purity of a solution of nucleic acid is determined by measuring the absorbance of the solution at two wave length, usually 260nm and 280nm, and calculating the ratio of A_{260}/A_{280} [20]. It can also be assessed by measuring 260/280 and 260/230 as reported by Chong et al., [21]. Groups A, B, NC and D have higher purity of 2.04, 2.05, 2.01 and 2.02 at A_{260}/A_{280} , and a A_{260}/A_{230} absorbance ratio of 2.12, 2.08, 2.06 and 1.86, respectively, which support the finding of Desjardins and Conklin, [20].

Also, according to Inscho et al., [22], 260/280 absorbance ratio having values between 1.8 and 2.0, and 260/230 ratio of values within 1.8 and 2.2 showed that RNA was clear of contamination. Groups E, F, G, H, I, and J showed a purity levels of 2.07, 2.08, 2.09, 2.09, 2.11 and 2.08 at A_{260}/A_{280} , and 2.16, 2.06, 2.06, 1.89, 2.17 and

1.95 at A_{260}/A_{230} respectively. These observations indicate reduced purity in comparison to other group, although their purity level is still within acceptable range for downstream analysis. As such, the values obtained from these groups still align with the report of Desjardins and Conklin [19] as well as Chong et al. [21]. Furthermore, all the groups revealed a higher concentration of extracted RNA in the different cultivar of eggplants. Therefore, the values obtained from the purity check showed that the RNA samples are sufficiently pure enough to be used for gene expression studies.

The amplification cycle of *SGTI* gene in the different eggplants samples were notably increased across the group, with sample B having the lowest amplification cycle and highest gene expression (3.87%); the lower the amplification cycles the higher the expression of the target gene. Therefore, sample B with Cq value of 36.41 agree with the report of Walker, [23] who stated that the more copies of target gene in the input of the reaction, the fewer the cycles of amplification required to attain the amount of amplification output related with the quantification threshold, as such the *SGTI* gene is more in sample B compare to group NC, E, and J. Also, sample A, D, F, G, H and I showed no Cq values for the target gene which indicate absence of *SGTI* gene in these samples, which suggest little or no solasonine content in this group of samples.

The fold change in expression of target gene (*SGTI*) in the samples B (0.41), NC (1.00), E (0.71) and J (0.65) is lowered, because of the matured fruit of different cultivar of eggplants used in this study. This agrees with the findings of Bagheriet al. [24] that reported fold change of 21.82 and 14.97 for young and matured fruits respectively. Though the fold change in expression of *SGTI* gene in matured fruit obtained by Bagheriet al. [24] is higher, which could be due to differences in the level of matured eggplant fruits used in their study compared to this study. Since the expression of *SGTI* gene is associated with the maturity of the fruit, therefore, reduced or no expression observed in this finding align with Bagheriet al. [24] and other previous reports. Further still, samples A, D, F, G, H, I and J having a fold change of zero, is an indicative of loss of expression of *SGTI* gene, this is also reflected in the phenotypic characteristic of these groups of eggplants having a colour such as green and white and purple, as oppose to predominant green

observed in samples B, NC and E. Also, low or no expression of *SGTI* gene, which translates to little or no solasonine content, could make samples A, D, F, G, H, I and J palatable to people. *SGTI* expression had been found to correlate with solasonine production in eggplant fruits which by extension is linked to the variation in bitterness experienced from consuming different cultivars of eggplant fruits. This discovery supports the findings of Padmanabhan et al. [25] that high concentration of solasonine and melongosides in the fruit can cause bitterness, making the fruit unappealing or unpalatable. The level of bitterness in eggplant fruits is influenced by, but not limited to, cultivars and fruit maturity among others. In other words, the more mature an eggplant fruit is, the lower the level of solasonine and the lesser the bitterness of the fruit.

5.0 Conclusion

This study gives an understanding regarding variation in gene expression of *SGTI* in various cultivars of matured eggplant fruits. Also, there is a remarkable relationship between the expression level of *SGTI*, solasonine production and cultivar types of matured eggplant fruit. As such we can conclude that solasonine content of eggplant fruit is related to *SGTI* gene expression level, which in turn affect the extent of bitterness in eggplant fruits especially when the fruit is matured.

6.0 Recommendation

It was observed from this study that samples A, D, F, G, H and I which cut across both *S. gilo* and *S. melongena* did not show expression and production of solasonine, thereby making them not bitter and suitable for consumption. Therefore, we recommend to farmers and eggplant breeders to ensure that they allow fruits of these crops to maturity before harvesting them for human consumption.

7.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors report that there are no competing interests to declare

8.0 Reference

- [1] Mohamed SA, Emam AM, Hawash H, Abul-Soud M. Producing Eggplant by Using Sustainable Urban Horticulture. Egypt J of Appl Sci, 2022; 37:1-2
- [2] FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO. The State of Food Security and

- Nutrition in the World 2023. Urbanization, agrifood systems transformation and healthy diets across the rural–urban continuum. Rome, FAO. 2023; <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc3017en>
- [3] Santos, M., Moreira, H., Cabral, J. A., Gabriel, R., Teixeira, A., Bastos, R., Aires, A. Contribution of Home Gardens to Sustainable Development: Perspectives from A Supported Opinion Essay. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022; 21;19(20):13715. doi: 10.3390/ijerph192013715. PMID: 36294295; PMCID: PMC9603381.
- [4] Lelario, F., De Maria, S., Rivelli, A. R., Russo, D., Milella, L., Bufo, S. A., and Scrano, L. A Complete Survey of Glycoalkaloids Using LC-FTICR-MS and IRMPD in a Commercial Variety and a Local Landrace of Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) and their Anticholinesterase and Antioxidant Activities. *Toxins*: 2019; 11(4), 230; <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins11040230>
- [5] Chowański, S.; Adamski, Z.; Marciniak, P.; Rosiński, G.; Büyükgüzel, E.; Büyükgüzel, K. *et al.* A review of bioinsecticidal activity of Solanaceae alkaloids. *Toxins*. 2016; **8**: 60.
- [6] Milner, S.E., Brunton, N.P., Jones, P.W., O'Brien, N.M., Collins, S.G., Maguire, A.R. Bioactivities of Glycoalkaloids and Their Aglycones from *Solanum* Species. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*; 2011; **59**: 3454–3484.
- [7] Hameed, A., Ijaz, S., Mohammad, I.S., Muhammad, K.S., Akhtar, N., Khan, H. M.S. Aglycone solanidine and solasodine derivatives: A natural approach towards cancer. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*; 2017; **94**: 446–457.
- [8] Spochacz, M., Chowański, S., Szymczak, M., Lelario, F., Bufo, S., Adamski, Z. Sublethal Effects of *Solanum nigrum* Fruit Extract and Its Pure Glycoalkaloids on the Physiology of *Tenebrio molitor* (Mealworm). *Toxins*, 2018; **10**: 504-505
- [9] Yazaki, K. ABC transporters involved in the transport of plant secondary metabolites. *FEBS letters*; **580**:2006; 1183-1191.
- [10] De Luca, V. and Laflamme, P. The expanding universe of alkaloid biosynthesis. *Current Opinion in Plant Biology*; 2001; **4**: 225-233.
- [11] Rezaei, M., Naghavi, M.R., Hoseinzade, A.H., Abbasi, A. Developmental accumulation of thebaine and some gene transcripts in different organs of *Papaver bracteatum*. *Industrial Crops and Products*; 2016; **80**: 262–268.
- [12] Al Sinani, S.S.S. and Eltayeb, E.A. The steroidal glycoalkaloids solamargine and solasonine in *Solanum* plants. *South African Journal of Botany*. 2017; **112**: 253–269.
- [13] Mariot, R.F., de Oliveira, L.A., Voorhuijzen, M., Staats, M., Hutten, R., Van Dijk, J.P. Characterization and transcriptional profile of genes involved on glycoalkaloid biosynthesis in new varieties of *Solanum tuberosum* L. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*; 2016; **64**: 988-996.
- [14] Friedman, M. Chemistry and anticarcinogenic mechanisms of glycoalkaloids produced by eggplants, potatoes, and tomatoes. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*; 2015; **63**: 3323–3337.
- [15] Friedman, M. Potato glycoalkaloids and metabolites: roles in the plant and in the diet. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*; 2006; **54**: 8655–8681.
- [16] Prohens, J., Anderson, G. J., Rodriguez-Burruezo, A., Nuez, F. Exploiting wild species for the genetic improvement of the pepino (*Solanum muricatum*). *Journal of Applied Botany and Food Quality*; 2003; **77**: 21–27.
- [17] Sánchez-Mata, M.C., Yokoyama, W.E., Hong, Y.J., Prohens, J. α -Solasodine and α -solasolamargine contents of gboma (*Solanum macrocarpon* L.) and scarlet (*Solanum aethiopicum* L.) eggplants. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*; 2010; **58**: 5502-5508.
- [18] Yuan, C., Li, C., Zhao, X. Yan, C., Wang, J., Mou, Y. *et al.* Genome-Wide Identification and Characterization of *HSP90-RAR1-SGT1*-Complex Members from *Arachis* Genomes

- and their Responses to Biotic and Abiotic Stresses. *Frontiers in Genetics* 12. 2021RL=<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/genetics/articles/10.3389/fgene.2021.689669> DOI=10.3389/fgene.2021.689669. ISSN=1664-8021
- [19] Livak, K. J. and Schmittgen, T. Analysis of relative gene expression data using real-time quantitative PCR and the 2-DDCt method. *Methods* 2001; 25(4):402–408.
- [20] Desjardins, P. and Conklin, D. Nanodrop micro-volume quantitation of nucleic acids. *Journal of visualized experiments*. 2010; 45: 25-65.
- [21] Chong, G. O., Han, H. S., Lee, S. D. and Lee, Y. H. Improvement in RNA quantity and quality in cervico-vaginal cytology. *Virology Journal*; 2020; 17(1): 8-10.
- [22] Inscho, E. W, Wilfinger, W. W, Banks, R. O. Dissociation and enrichment of rat atrial myocytes containing atrial natriuretic factor (ANF). *Hormonal Research* 1986; 24(1):26-37. doi: 10.1159/000180536. PMID: 3019859.
- [23] Walker N.J. Tech Sight. A technique whose time has come. *Science*. 2002; 296: 557–559.
- [24] Bagheri, M., Bushehri, A. A. S., Hassandokht, M. R. and Naghavi, M. R. Evaluation of Solasonine Content and Expression Patterns of *SGTI* Gene in Different Tissues of Two Iranian Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.). Genotypes. *Food technology and biotechnology*. 2017; 55(2): 236–242.
- [25] Padmanabhan, P., Cheema, A. and Paliyath, G. Solanaceous Fruits Including Tomato, Eggplant, and Peppers. *Encyclopedia of Food and Health*, Academic Press 2016; pages 24–32.

